

Alla CHASTINA

Doctor în studiul artelor, Institutul Patrimoniului Cultural. Domenii de interes științific: arhitectură, istorie. Cărți publicate: *Архитекторы Бессарабии (первая половина XIX века)*, Chișinău: Garomont Studio, 2018.

THE CREATIVITY OF ARCHITECT G. TORICELLI (1796–1843)

This year marks 155th anniversary of the construction of Kishinev Prison Castle. Its author's the famous Odessa architect George Toricelli, who is also known for creating another historic building in Chishinau as the Lutheran Church. Both were important enough to be reproduced on the city's views as its symbol.

G. Toricelli was born in 1796 in Lugano, Switzerland to a family of architects, some of whom had been known to work in Northern Italy and Southern Switzerland (Certain architect Felice Torcello, performed some work in the Basilica of St. Dominic in Bologna at the beginning of the XVIII century) as well as in St. Petersburg [1, p. 239]. In 1818 Toricelli arrived in Odessa, where for 6 years worked under guidance of architect Francesco Boffo and evidently worked on the developing of residential model projects, as well as participated in the building of the first St Paul's Lutheran Church (not in existence) and the Customs Building at the port of Odessa. In 1822–1832 as a young architect, Toricelli further masters his skills by participating in building of Pokrovsky Cathedral in Izmail, – project of A. I. Melnikov, professor of Architecture from St. Petersburg.

Soon after successfully passing exams in 1826, apparently in architecture, G. Toricelli is hired as an assistant to a city architect by the Odessa Building Committee and by the year 1828, he already serves as appointed city architect in the Odessa 2nd part where develops his own projects.

In 1832 he designs a two-story mansion with a small garden for staff-captain Horvat, – a building in Italian High Renaissance style. The characteristics of the early style of G. Toricelli drew attention of researcher of architecture Piliavsky V. A, who noted that the architect gravitated to “late-Gothic and Palladian motifs”, typical for representatives of Northern Italian (Lombard and Venetian) and Tessinian architectural styles [2, p. 11].

In 1838 the building was purchased by Count Tolstoy (Ukrainian branch of the well-known clan). Today the building is the Odessa Scientists' House at 4, Sabaneyev Bridge.

Participation in the construction of the old Odessa Merchant's Exchange on the Promenade was an important step in his professional development, but even more so, was the architect's collaboration in completion of the Transfiguration Cathedral.

Kishinev Lutheran Church

Kishinev Prison Castle

The Cathedral, creation of a few generations of prominent architects and artists who worked on its construction since 1795, becomes not only a monumental religious building, but also a memorial complex – the burial place of Odessa bishops and other important personalities. Among those were Novorossiysk and Bessarabian Governor-General Prince Michael Vorontsov and his wife.

In 1825 designed by architect George Franolli the construction begins of the three-tiered bell tower of the cathedral, which, for unknown reasons, was suspended in 1827, and 9 years later – in 1836 was continued already by architect G. Toricelli. The unusual four-tiered bell tower, with its characteristic for the architect features, was solemnly consecrated in 1837.

George Toricelli was a multifaceted master, famous for his architectural ensembles. One of which is a complex of squares, uniting in the center of Odessa a many administrative, cultural and community centers, such as his elegant arcade in Exchange Square, City Club at the Theatre Square and 44 shops of the Palais Royal [3, p. 39].

In 1838 designed by G. Toricelli in Kishinev was built the Lutheran church, unfortunately, destroyed in the 1960s.

Single-nave, rectangular in plan, covered by gable roof church building, on the west side of which was attached a high tower. It was de-

signed to house the town clock. The semicircular apse was completing the building on the east side. “High lancet shaped windows, decorative turrets - all vaguely reminiscent of Gothic forms and are believed to have been executed by Toricelli, to satisfy the requirements of rich German colonists” [4, p. 23].

G. Toricelli took an active part in the construction of a prison fortress in the city of Kishinev [5, p. 58-69].

Designed as a medieval castle, the building was constructed from 1834 to 1864. Alike the castle-fortress, the prison represented a single closed volume with the impregnable battlements and a sufficiently large space inside the yard. The tall structure dominated the city’s skyline and resembled a medieval Moorish castle. Under the plan, it was a square with cut corners, on each axis were four bastions, flanked by special projections of rectangular towers. There, “the sham buttresses, slightly raised from the surface of the walls, which, however, in combination with overall irregularity in wall’s footprint created an interesting interplay of light and shadow” [6, p. 153].

12 November 1864 a new “Prison was opened where the prisoners from the old prison, the one on Skulyansky fork were transferred to. This prison has cost nearly a million, and was considered at one time a model building” [7, p. 1]. Inner space of the “castle” was filled

with buildings of different economic purpose, by prisoners' cells bound by the common corridors and stairways, with the church and medical office consisting of male and female parts. For all the rigors of the prison, the building exuded romanticism, George Toricelli received a reputation of being one "of the most successful architects – "romanticists" [8, p. 154] of the first half of the XIX century.

There are other works of the architect Toricelli, among them – the Church of St. John Chrysostom in Yalta, created in collaboration with architects Aeschlimann and Devaux. As it was popular for the Russian architecture of the 20-40 of the XIX century to combine the Romantic elements of eclectic style with those of Gothic, the church was designed by the type of rural churches in England with the use of Gothic elements in the facade and interior. To this end, G. Torricelli is using a number of techniques characteristic of the English Gothic churches: gable end of aisles (one can see it even now), the bell tower with a pyramidal hipped top (not preserved), a lancet window and door openings (existing), windows decorated with stained glass.

Architect George Toricelli was invited to design a church in Alushta, in the creation of which actively participated Governor-General of Novorossiysk and Bessarabia Prince M. S. Vorontsov (1782–1856), who favored architectural style for the Southern Coast reminiscent of medieval castles and churches in Britain. For the fulfillment of a wish Novorossiysk Prince, architect G. Toricelli, like before, has used the traditional architectural techniques of the English Gothic. Original wooden structures were open gaze: a wooden ceiling, the lancet-shaped doorways and colorful stained glass windows. The Temple looked unusual for Orthodox Christians who were accustomed to a more rigorous "Byzantine" style of church architecture. Upon

completion, 30 November 1842, the church was solemnly consecrated in the name of St. Theodore Stratelates, the patron saint of the ruling Romanovs. Judging from old photographs and engravings with views of Alushta, belfry, built in the characteristic style of the author, served as an architectural example for the whole city. The church is a masonry single-nave, cross-like in foot print to which was attached three-tiered bell tower. The architect uses the same features characteristic of the architecture of English Gothic churches: gable end of the lateral limits, the bell tower with a pyramidal hipped top, the lancet-shaped windows and doorways, tall buttresses, jagged parapets to top facades. Carved iconostasis of the church was carried out according to the designs of the architect, G. I. Toricelli of basswood.

In the years 1830–1840 George Toricelli took part, along with other prominent Italian architects, in the creation of a delicate interior of the Yusupov Palace in St. Petersburg, located by the river Moyka.

Knowledge of history of architecture, sense of style and overall erudition, allowed the architect George Toricelli to be offered in 1835 a project of creation of the Museum of Antiquities in Kerch, on the eastern slope of Mount Mithridates. For the museum building was chosen the style of a small antique temple, symbolically reproducing the presence of Greek colonies in Colchis.

In the second half of the XIX century, this building of the former museum of antiquities has still decorated the mountainside, overlooking the central city square. Damaged during the Crimean War it was then given to the Orthodox community of the city (not preserved).

In 1830–1840 George Toricelli designed, commissioned by Count M. S. Vorontsov, Transfiguration Church in Moshna, near Cher-

kassy, the architecture of which was in the same style of English Gothic, Tudor Gothic with Oriental motifs. For its architectural style, it is reminiscent of a former Lutheran church in Kishinev, as well as the famous Vorontsov Palace in Alupka. Despite the use of oriental decor, architect followed the principles of the Orthodox cross-domed building. The temple and connected to it a 50-meter bell tower create a coherent whole. Above crossing – the largest flattened as per the eastern traditions dome. Giving special charm to the building are the numerous elegant turrets, which along with the lancet windows highlight the Gothic style of the tall quadrangular steeple.

The premature death of George Toricelli in 1843 didn't allow completing his many architectural projects. But and today all preserved monuments attract to peculiar refinement, monumental strictness with the fineness of order décor.

The creativity of architect G. Toricelli (1796–1843)

Summary. This article is connected with the name of famous architect George Toricelli (1796–1843) who was an Italian by birth. Also he was originated from the architect dynasty. Earlier there was the Lutheran church in Kishinev, but this monument was lost in the 1960s. It is known, that also George Toricelli projected some buildings in Odesa, Ismail. This year we mark the 155th anniversary of the construction of Kishinev Prison castle, which was built from 1834 to 1864 according to the project of architect Toricelli. It is the architectural monument and partially preserving before our days.

Key words: Italian architectural school, architect, Prison castle, Lutheran church, gothic style, architectural project, Kishinev, first half of XIX century.

Creația arhitectului G. Toricelli (1796–1843)

Rezumat. Prezentul articol este consacrat arhitectului din Odessa Giorgio Toricelli (1796–1843), reprezentant de referință al dinastiei italiene de arhitecți. La Chișinău creația sa este cunoscută grație monumentelor arhitecturale, dispărute deja, Chirha luterană și Penitenciarul, construite după proiectele sale în prima jumătate a secolului al XIX-lea. Arhitectul a proiectat clădiri și în Odessa, Ismail. În acest an se împlinesc 155 de ani de la construirea Penitenciarului, clădire care s-a păstrat doar parțial, fiind inclusă în lista monumentelor de arhitectură.

Cuvinte-cheie: școala italiană de arhitectură, arhitect, Penitenciar, Chirha luterană, stilul gotic, proiect arhitectural, Chișinău, prima jumătate a secolului XIX.

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